

An analysis of constraints associated with household waste reduction and reuse practices

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ABSTRACT

Birth and death is the crucial part of any creature in the universe. But whatever left in between birth and death is the human inference, which can be a best gift or a worst sin depends upon the human activity on the resources. Resources are very limited in nature, it is the duty of each and everyone to protect and preserve the resources for prospect generation. Limited resources should not be treated as waste; nothing is waste unless it is properly reduced, reused and recycled. In common man's view anything which is not needed anymore is the waste. Scientifically speaking, there is no waste in the world, anything and everything can be transformed into a useful thing. Domestic waste is the common type of waste which everyone comes across. The study is based on the analysis of awareness among the people on domestic waste and the emerging difficulties in waste reduction and reuse practise. This study is conducted by preparing likerts scale questionnaire through focus group interaction with the household women's. The study focused on Mangalore region by collecting opinions by 384 respondents.

Key words:Emerging problems, Human interference, Waste reduce and reuse.

Introduction

Solid waste may in the form of organic and inorganic, which is generated by households and commercial activities. Waste generated by households is usually disposed into communal bins that are designed from metal, made from concrete or inclusion of both. Street waste sweepings also transferred to community bins. These community waste bins are also used by other commercial sectors for disposal. Some households, commercial, industrial waste depend on municipality for transfer of their waste to disposal area by paying some amount in municipal taxes (Kumar et al., 2009). Municipal solid waste management is a critical element towards sustainable development of the country. This includes segregation, storage, collection, transportation, processing, and disposal of solid waste to minimize its negative impact on environment and the society. Ineffective management of waste becomes a prime factor responsible of innumerable predicament (Kumar et al., 2009). In India, rapid development of urbanization, modernisation and ineffective measure on growth rate of population are main reasons to become a serious issue in regard to waste management (Annepu, 2012). The projected urban population is 33.4 % by the year 2026. The quantum of waste generated in Indian region is increasing day by day on account of its increasing population and increased GDP. The yearly quantity of solid waste generated in Indian region has increased from 6 million tons in 1947 to 48 million tons in 1997 with an annual growth rate of 4.25%, and it is expected to rise to 300 million tons by 2047 (CPCB, 1998). There is an unorganized and no scientifically planned segregation, collection, storage of municipal waste either at domestic level or at community bins. Separation of waste takes places under very unsafe and hazardous circumstances and the effectiveness of segregation is considerably low in unorganized sector (Kaushal, Varghese & Chabukdhara 2012). On a many instance, due to improper handling of the segregated waste constituents got mixed up again during carriage and disposal (CPCB Report, 2013). Lack of segregation knowledge deprive proper scientific waste disposal (Singhal & Pandey 2000). The crucial activities like collecting materials from the waste, which could be gainfully recuperate and utilized for making useful item. Since non-segregated waste is dumped at community bins, its recycling becomes difficult when the different kinds of wastes are mixed up. However, garbage pickers usually separate it and took and sell those materials which can be used for recycling like plastics, glass, metal, iron etc. (Pattnaik & Reddy 2010).

It is notable that each and every person in the world has contributed for waste generation. If each and every person contributed for the waste reduction, reuse, recycle there will not be any waste related problem in the earth.

Objectives

1. To find out the constraints connected with reduction and reuse of the waste at household level.
2. To provide suggestions to reduce and reuse waste at households.
3. To analyse the relationship between awareness level & problems connected to the domestic waste reduction and reuse.

Research methods

Focus group interaction was conducted with 12 household women's before preparing the questionnaire and selecting sample size. This paper is based on primary data collected from 384 households in Mangalore region of Karnataka. The collected data has been analyzed using chi square test to evaluate the awareness and constraints for households in regards to domestic waste reduction and reuse practices. A structured questionnaire was designed with 5 point likerts scale, which focused on the objectives of the study. Secondary information was sourced from research papers from research scholar and research gate, journals, book and magazines.

Limitations

Waste is of different forms like solid waste, liquid waste, industrial waste, agricultural waste, e-waste, medicine waste, biodegradable waste and more. This research paper concentrated only domestic solid waste reduction and reuse practices. Domestic liquid waste aspect is not considered for the study. The opinions of the respondents is collected through questionnaire, some personal bias of the respondents may affect the study to certain extent.

Literature review

Dr. Raveesh Agarwal et al (2015) in his paper on waste management initiatives in India for human well being reported that to achieve financial, socio-economic and environmental sustainability goals in the field of waste management, there is a need to systematically and scientifically analyze the SWOT of the community as well as the municipal corporation, based on which an effective waste management system can be evolved with the participation of various stakeholders in India. The public apathy can be altered by awareness building campaigns and educational measures. Sensitization of the community is also essential to achieve the above objectives and we need to act and act fast as every city in India is already a

hotbed of many contagious diseases, most of which are caused by ineffective waste management.

Nivya Noonhiyil Kaithery et al (2019), the research paper revealed that perpetual insight and on the field training activities should be undertaken for the effective waste disposal, recycling and reusing of the unwanted things. Majority of population in rural area of north kerala showed above average interest towards daily management of household waste. Women play a key role in household waste separation, recycling, reuse and disposal of the household waste

J.C. Hargreaves et al (2008), research study showed that, Waste management process can be made effective by separating the waste at the generating point itself, Because Recyclables materials are not separated at emerging point and are mixed with organic waste thus making it difficult to separate. The general municipal solid waste problem of developing countries, especially in Asia is that waste separation is not effectively implemented. Further, the moisture level of the mixed waste is high. This high moisture level is true especially in countries like India, Indonesia, Sri-lanka, Bangladesh, Malaysia and Thailand. However, the potential of these high moisture waste to be made into compost is ruined by the contamination of hazardous waste which is included in the mixed waste, making it a lower quality, if not, toxic containing compost that farmers are reluctant to buy and apply to their crops.

Ali Akbar Babaei et al (2015), the research paper identifies that the population in the study area are showing positive interest towards separation of waste according to its category and reducing and reusing the household waste but they have less knowledge of different process separation and reuse of unwanted things. The age group, education level, gender, occupation, profession, family size, life style, consumerism factors have influence on waste segregation techniques. The various training programmes should be designed by concentrating on females because the waste management at home is looked after by the females.

Z. Minghua et al (2009), the study showed that people who frequently go to the community bins to dispose of general waste are more likely to refuse the recycling and reuse of some product at home, and in most cases, as the distance to the community bins reduces, the number of citizens separating and reusing the waste at home increases. In order to increase recycling, the government should encourage markets for recycled product at a reasonable price by giving subsidies to such companies and increasing proficiency in recycling companies.

Pratheeksha and Dr. KVM Varambally (2020), the study conducted in the Mangalore region regarding the awareness of household waste management reveals that Swacch Bharath programme have positive impact on the domestic waste management, which lead to separation of dry waste and wet waste. 71% of the respondent are aware of the waste reduction, recycle and reuse.

Discussion

Data analysis and interpretation

Problems connected with domestic waste reduction and reuse

A 5-point Likert-type scale was created to measure the respondents' problems connected with domestic waste reduction and reuse practices in the study area. The questionnaire with the range of Strongly Agree (1), Agree (2), Neutral (3), Disagree (4) and Strongly Disagree (5) were used. Accordingly, the study exhibits the top priority problems connected with domestic waste reduction and reuse practices in the study area by the ranking system presented in Table 1:

- ❖ Total number of respondents = 384
- ❖ 'W' stand for Weighted sum
- ❖ 'M' stand for Mean
- ❖ 'S' stand for Standard Deviation
- ❖ "R" stand for Rank

Table 1

Distribution of respondents' Problems connected with domestic waste reduction and reuse.

No	Reasons	1	2	3	4	5	W	M	SD	R
1.	Blind belief	189	109	12	46	28	767	1.997	1.288	4
2.	Too much depend on waste collection service	103	197	42	36	06	797	2.076	0.941	5
3.	Status and life style	88	156	58	56	26	928	2.417	1.183	10
4.	Effect of online shopping	92	184	52	38	18	854	2.294	1.088	8
5.	No permission for pets in Flats/apartment	282	95	05	02	00	495	1.289	0.512	2
6.	Not interested in pets	58	63	152	68	43	1127	2.935	1.177	14
7.	Not carrying their own bags while purchasing	109	96	81	66	32	968	2.521	1.289	11

8.	Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell	294	35	19	31	05	570	1.484	0.995	3
9.	Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen	89	201	58	23	13	822	2.141	0.952	6
10.	Health conscious makes the people to keep medicines as a security.	68	193	28	35	60	978	2.547	1.312	12
11.	Some of the food waste i.e., used cooking oil, can't be reused for other food making	59	92	152	35	46	1069	2.784	1.174	13
12.	Lack of awareness	103	132	96	42	11	878	2.286	1.064	7
13.	Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.)	293	84	03	03	01	487	1.268	0.448	1
14.	Laziness/ outside work pressure	98	124	84	62	16	926	2.411	1.152	9
Overall score or Mean & S D		138	126	60	39	21	831	2.164	1.178	--

Source: Field survey

The above Table reveals that the average scores or Mean and Standard Deviation for the entire 14 component on problems connected with waste reduction and reuse is 2.164& 1.178. The study shows that, Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.)with (Mean is 1.268& S D is 0.448), No permission for pets in Flats/apartment (Mean is 1.289& S D is 0.512), Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell(Mean is 1.484& S D is 0.995),Blind belief (Mean is 1.997& S D is 1.288), Too much depend on waste collection service (Mean is 2.076& S D is 0.941), and Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen(Mean is 2.141& S D is 0.952) are the prominent problems in the study area because, Mean and Standard Deviations are less than the overall score or Mean & S D.

The reasons, such as Lack of awareness(Mean is 2.286& S D is 1.064), Effects of online shopping (Mean is 2.294& S D is 1.088), Laziness/ outside work pressure(Mean is 2.411& S D is 1.152), Status and life style (Mean is 2.417& S D is 1.183), Not carrying their own bags while purchasing (Mean is 2.521& S D is 1.289), Health conscious makes the people to keep medicines as a security(Mean is 2.547& S D is 1.312), Some of the food waste i.e., used cooking oil, can't be reused for other food making (Mean is 2.784& S D is 1.174) and Not

interested in pets (Mean is 2.935 & S D is 1.177) are least resulted the problems in the study area because their respective mean and SD are more than the overall score or Mean & S D.

Chi-square Analysis

Relationship between awareness level & problems connected to the domestic waste reduction and reuse.

Among the 14 problems connected with waste reduction and reuse practices in this study, the analysis purpose the prominent 6 constraints are considered. They are: Blind belief, Too much depend on waste collection service, No permission for pets in Flats/apartment, Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell, Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen and Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.).

Table 2
Awareness level & Blind belief

Awareness Level	Blind belief					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Strongly agree	75	34	03	13	07	132
Agree	65	39	05	17	11	137
Neutral	13	10	01	04	03	31
Disagree	17	19	02	09	05	52
Strongly disagree	19	07	01	03	02	32
Total	189	109	12	46	28	384

Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Blind belief) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse. We make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Blind belief) do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 12.78$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **12.78** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of

domestic waste management & reasons (Blind belief) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse are independent on each other.

Table 3
Awareness level & Too much depend on waste collection service

Awareness level	Too much depend on waste collection service					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Strongly agree	30	76	13	11	02	132
Agree	38	64	17	15	03	137
Neutral	11	15	03	02	00	31
Disagree	14	26	06	05	01	52
Strongly disagree	10	16	03	03	00	32
Total	103	197	42	36	06	384

Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Too much depend on waste collection service). We make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Too much depend on waste collection service) for not reusing and reducing the waste do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 6.67$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **6.67** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Too much depend on waste collection service) for not reusing and reducing the waste are independent on each other.

Table 4
Awareness level & No permission for pets in Flats/apartment

Awareness level	No permission for pets in Flats/apartment					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	

Strongly agree	99	30	02	01	00	132
Agree	98	36	02	01	00	137
Neutral	23	08	00	00	00	31
Disagree	39	12	01	00	00	52
Strongly disagree	23	09	00	00	00	32
Total	282	95	05	02	00	384

Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (No permission for pets in Flats/apartment) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse. We make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (No permission for pets in Flats/apartment) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 1.00$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **1.00** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (No permission for pets in Flats/apartment) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse is independent on each other.

Table 5

Awareness level & Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell

Awareness level	Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Strongly agree	108	08	08	07	01	132
Agree	108	12	05	12	00	137
Neutral	22	04	01	03	01	31
Disagree	41	04	02	04	01	52
Strongly disagree	15	07	03	05	02	32

Total	294	35	19	31	05	384
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Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse. We make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 22.32$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **22.32** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Non veg packing plastic can't be reused because of smell) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse are independent on each other.

Table 6

Awareness level & Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen

Awareness level	Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Strongly agree	26	79	16	07	04	132
Agree	29	73	20	10	05	137
Neutral	10	11	06	03	01	31
Disagree	16	22	11	01	02	52
Strongly disagree	08	16	05	02	01	32
Total	89	201	58	23	13	384

Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse. We

may make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 14.07$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **14.07** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Old Nylon and other kinds of clothes can't be used in kitchen) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse are independent on each other.

Table 7

Awareness level & Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.)

Awareness level	Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.)					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Strongly agree	107	24	01	00	00	132
Agree	105	29	01	01	01	137
Neutral	23	06	01	01	00	31
Disagree	39	12	00	01	00	52
Strongly disagree	19	13	00	00	00	32
Total	293	84	03	03	01	384

Source: Field Survey

Here, we apply chi-square test to examine whether there exists any relationship between Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse. We make a null hypothesis that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse do not depend on each other. Under the null hypothesis, we calculate the value of chi-square statistic as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{N(ad - bc)^2}{(a + b)(a + c)(b + c)(b + d)}$$

$$\chi^2 = 6.41$$

From the table of chi-square probabilities, we have, $\chi^2_{0.05}(16) = 26.296$

As the computed value **6.41** is less than the table value (**26.296**), the hypothesis is to be accepted at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we conclude that the Awareness level of domestic waste management & reasons (Sharp materials can't be reused (bulb, tube, knife etc.) connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse independent on each other.

Suggestions

The above chi square analysis relating to the certain reason connected with difficulty in waste reduction and reuse practices are independent to each other. It proves that giving only awareness is not sufficient to manage the waste. The government should undertake certain motivational activities to reduce the waste at generation point. i.e, at household level. For example giving tax benefit for the people who disposes less waste to the collection point, providing waste disposal bins to each houses to separate wet waste and dry waste, providing training to women to prepare art and craft by waste items, encouraging students by conducting healthy competition at school and college level regarding reuse of waste materials etc.

At macro level: Encouraging the production of recycled product by giving subsidy to such industries, making a strict rules regarding the collection of waste wrappers or bottles from the customer by the supplying/ manufacturing industry, discouraging one time usage product i.e, use and throw plastics, plates, bottle etc.

Conclusion

Households face many difficulties in waste reduction and reuse practices i.e, blind belief, sharp materials, too much dependency on waste collection service, different non reusable clothes and some of materials etc. The study concluded that all the difficulties are not dependent on awareness level; it is independent to each other. Creating awareness is not only sufficient, to achieve the goal of waste reduction and reuse of waste at generation point. And it requires continuous observation from the concerned local authorities with regard to domestic waste reduction techniques. The government must introduce strict rules and regulations i.e, negative taxation, promotional or supporting practices at the household levels.

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